

EFFECT OF COUNSELING ON SMOKING CESSATION IN PATIENTS OF CORONARY ARTERY DISEASE

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Abstract

Introduction: Smoking is still a major preventable cause of illness and mortality globally, and the causal association of smoking with cardiovascular disease, including CAD, has been firmly established. Successful smoking cessation therapy is an essential part of management and risk reduction for smoking-dependent patients, especially those with established cardiovascular disease.

Objective: To determine the mean smoking cessation score of counselling of smoking cessation in patient of coronary artery disease

Study Design: Quasi experimental trial

Place and Duration of Study: Department of Cardiology, Armed Forces Institute of Cardiology Rawalpindi from May 15, 2025 to August 14, 2025.

Methodology: 105 male and female 18-65-year-old known patients of coronary artery disease (one, two, or three major heart arteries (coronary arteries) having >50% occlusion, diagnosed on coronary angiography) and active smokers were enrolled from AFIC OPD. Smokers with existing pharmacotherapy or counseling, cognitive impairment, lung disease, or psychiatric disease were excluded. The design for the study was a quasi-experimental trial, and nonprobability consecutive sampling method was applied for patient selection. Data analysis was conducted using SPSS 22.

Results: Results of the study revealed that age, smoking history, dependent scores before and after a session, and changes in dependence scores were all shown to deviate from a normal distribution. Every variable showed a skewness away from normalcy, except for body mass index. Smoking dependence scores significantly improved after the intervention, falling from 29.0 to 14.0 on the Wilcoxon signed-rank test. The intervention was significant across all clinical and demographic subgroups, according to the stratified analysis.

Conclusion: In conclusion, current study demonstrated that the smoking cessation intervention functioned strongly to reduce scores for smoking dependence among participants. Statistically significant reduction in the entire sample and in all subgroups but one verifies the strong efficacy of the positive impact of the intervention. While results tend to be universal, statistical analysis reports that the magnitude of effect can be affected by certain demographic and clinical factors.

INTRODUCTION

Coronary artery disease, one of the world's most common causes of morbidity and mortality, is a massive burden on health resources. Cigarette smoking is a key modifiable risk factor for CAD. Smoking is one of the most significant risk factors for other diseases and is among the most crucial avoidable causes of death. The risk of recurrent myocardial infarction is significantly reduced by quitting smoking compared to continued smoking.^{1,2} Tobacco diseases are leading worldwide public health problems. Cigarettes will cause 10 million deaths annually worldwide in 2030, 70% of whom will live in low- and middle-income countries.^{3,4} Fifty percent of former smokers quit after having an acute cardiac disease. Quitting is mainly attributed to discharge prescriptions for cardiac rehab, lack of depressed affect, and coronary surgery upon index hospitalization.^{5,6}

Proper attention should be given to these areas, as cardiac rehabilitation will continue to evolve as a beneficial and easily accessible intervention in the coming years.⁷

Cardiac rehabilitation is evidence-based treatment that employs patient education, health behavior change, and exercise conditioning to enhance secondary prevention outcomes in CAD patients. Evidence reveals that 20% of hospitalized CAD patients were smokers.⁸ Recommendations for the treatment of tobacco dependence advocate for the use of supportive systems, policies, and environmental reminders by healthcare facilities to promote and facilitate routine and effective identification and treatment of tobacco users.⁸ Quitting smoking after the development of symptomatic CAD decreases mortality risk. Although the CAD risk following smoking cessation is halved to a maximum of 50% within one year of quitting, after three to four years it is as low as that of a lifetime non-smoker. The advantages of stopping in reducing CAD risks are not confined to the young smokers only. Even among the elderly smokers aged more than 60 years, experience wipes out CAD risks after giving up smoking. It was realized in a study that approximately 73% of CAD patients, being habitual smokers, quit

smoking following counseling.⁹ Goetller et al.¹⁰ also realized that approximately 62.5% of patients discontinued smoking following counseling. Khan et al.¹¹ in a trial realized that the mean score of smoking at presentation was 29.50 ± 2.91 , which decreased to 14.40 ± 2.61 following a session of counseling in CAD patients.¹¹ The most powerful risk factor for CAD is smoking. Doctors play an important role in prevention of morbidity and mortality due to cigarette smoking.

Literature revealed that vast majority of CAD patients stopped smoking and had an incredible change in the scale of smoking dependence when they were counseled not to smoke cigarettes or tobacco. But for the local population, there is no valid evidence. Hence, we considered carrying out this study in order to have evidence for the local population. Primary care physicians/family physicians have repeated opportunities over several years to treat their smoking patients, and they are well placed to offer smoking cessation treatment and counseling. This shall assist us to sharpen our practice and skill, and if it is successful, thereafter, in the future, we shall incorporate counseling sessions as part of CAD management in a bid to motivate more individuals to stop smoking and enhance cardiac health. This shall ultimately lower myocardial infarction risk and the healthcare system burden.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was conducted after receiving approval from IERB. The quasi-experimental trial was conducted at the Department of Cardiology, Armed Forces Institute of Cardiology Rawalpindi, from May 15, 2025, to August 14, 2025. Using the WHO calculator, 105 subjects were identified with a 95% confidence level, $d=0.50$, and mean cigarette dependence scale score 14.40 ± 2.61 with counseling following CAD.¹¹ Nonprobability consecutive sampling was employed in the process of patient selection. Informed consent was obtained. Detailed history was obtained, e.g., patient's name, age, gender, BMI, smoking duration, CAD type (single, double, or triple vessel disease), alcoholism history, diabetes, hypertension, family

smoking history (father and brothers), occupation, home address, lifestyle, and socioeconomic status. Re-assessment of tobacco smoking dependence score at baseline was done for the patients. After two weeks of CAD, participants received counselling sessions from the researcher. Twice a week, a 60-minute session was made available either individually or in a group setting, as per situations. Counselling about the adverse effects of smoking, the advantages of quitting smoking, coping with the symptoms of withdrawal, and mechanisms of relapse prevention was the main agenda of the sessions. One of the self-help materials was a stop-smoking pamphlet containing information regarding the ill effects of smoking, advantages of stopping smoking, and stop-smoking methods. The OPD followed up patients for 1 month. Patients were rechecked on the 1-month dependence

on smoking. All data were noted in proforma. SPSS version 22 was used for data analysis. As Shapiro-Wilk normality test gave a statistically significant outcome ($p < 0.05$), the data were not normally distributed, a non-parametric equivalent of paired-samples t-test was needed. Hence, paired observations (pre-session and at 1 month) were compared by using the Wilcoxon signed-

rank test since it is non-parametric and suitable to compare related samples whose data can be uneven or even not normally distributed. Data were stratified for smoking dependence scores according to age, gender, CAD type, history of alcoholism, diabetes, hypertension, family history of smoking, lifestyle, and residence. Following stratification, Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test was utilized to contrast considerable differences in scores of smoking dependence.

RESULTS

Shapiro-Wilk test was applied to check normality of study variables (Table 1). Age (statistic = 0.947, $p < 0.001$), history of smoking (statistic = 0.973, $p = 0.031$), pre-session dependence score for smoking (statistic = 0.939, $p < 0.001$), post-session dependence score at one-month follow-up (statistic = 0.844, $p < 0.001$), and change in dependence score (statistic = 0.949, $p < 0.001$) were deviated from normal distribution. All variables except body mass index (BMI) (statistic = 0.982, $p = 0.162$) were skewed away from normality (Table-1). Non-parametric tests were applied for further analysis based on these observations.

Table-1: Shapiro-Wilk normality tests

Variables	Statistic	P value
Age	0.947	<0.001
BMI	0.982	0.162
Duration of smoking	0.973	0.031
Pre-session smoking dependence score	0.939	<0.001
Post-session after 1 month smoking dependence score	0.844	<0.001
Change in dependence score	0.949	<0.001

The mean age of the subjects was 41.0 years (mean=40.77±14.01 years). The median BMI was 24.2 kg/m² (mean = 24.99 ± 5.01), and the median length of time the subjects had been smoking was 28.0 (mean = 29.04 ± 9.40 years). The median pre-session measure of dependence on smoking was 29.0 (mean = 29.20 ± 1.54) and decreased to 14.0 (mean = 14.10 ± 0.84) at one-month follow-up. The median shift in the score

of dependence was 15.0 (mean = 15.10 ± 1.73). In categorical data, 52 (49.5%) were ≤ 40 years of age, and 53 (50.5%) were ≥ 41 years of age. Most of them were males, 95 (90.5%), compared to a meager 10 (9.5%) females. Alcohol consumption was mentioned by 9 (8.6%), whereas 96 (91.4%) were not alcoholic. Diabetes was found in 32 (30.5%) of the participants, and hypertension was found in 53 (50.5%). Family history of

Table-2: Descriptive statistics

Variables	Median	Mean±S.D
Quantitative Variables		
Age	41.0	40.77±14.01
BMI (kg/m ²)	24.2	24.99±5.01
Duration of smoking (year)	28.0	29.04±9.40
Pre-session smoking dependence score	29.0	29.20±1.54
After 1 month smoking dependence score	14.0	14.10±0.84
Change score	15.0	15.10±1.73
Categorical Variables		
	Number	Percentage
Age (Year)		
≤ 40	52	49.5
≥ 41	53	50.5
Gender		
Male	95	90.5
Female	10	09.5
Alcoholism		
Yes	09	08.6
No	96	91.4
Diabetes		
Yes	32	30.5
No	73	69.5
Hypertension		
Yes	53	50.5
No	52	49.5
Family history of smoking		
Yes	41	39.0
No	64	61.0
Occupation		
Employed	67	63.8
Unemployed	38	36.2
Lifestyle		
Active	39	37.1
Sedentary	66	62.9
Residence		
Rural	37	35.2
Urban	68	64.8
Socioeconomic status		
Low	33	31.4
Middle	59	56.2
High	13	12.4
Type of CAD		
Single vessel	29	27.6

Double vessel	44	41.9
Triple vessel	32	30.5

smoking was found in 41 (39.0%). 67 (63.8%) of the participants were employed and 38 (36.2%) were unemployed. Sedentary lifestyle was found more (66, 62.9%) than active lifestyle (39, 37.1%). Urban dwellers made up 68 (64.8%) of the participants, and 37 (35.2%) were rural dwellers. With respect to socioeconomic status, 59 (56.2%) were middle class, 33 (31.4%) were low socioeconomic status, and 13 (12.4%) were of high-income level. Of CAD, 29 (27.6%) were single-vessel, 44 (41.9%) were double-vessel, and 32 (30.5%) were triple-vessel disease (Table-2).

Wilcoxon signed-rank test showed statistically significant decrease in pre-session to one-month follow-up smoking dependence scores. The median score decreased from 29.0 to 14.0 with a median decrease of 15.0. The test returned a Z value of -8.928 and a $p < 0.001$ reflecting highly significant improvement after the intervention (Table-3).

Stratified Wilcoxon signed-rank test was utilized to ascertain whether the alteration in smoking dependence scores differed across demographic and clinical subgroups (Table 4). Age-stratified analysis revealed declines in both ≤ 40 years ($Z = -6.274, p < 0.001$) and ≥ 41 years ($Z = -6.334, p < 0.001$) age groups. Both men ($Z = -8.463, p < 0.001$) and women ($Z = -2.803, p < 0.001$) registered statistically significant reductions. CAD subgroups also exhibited significant decreases: single-vessel ($Z = -4.703, p < 0.001$), double-vessel ($Z = -5.776, p < 0.001$), and triple-vessel disease ($Z = -4.936$). In comorbid conditions, diabetic ($Z = -4.936, p < 0.001$) and non-diabetic ($Z = -7.424, p < 0.001$) groups, and hypertensive ($Z = -6.334, p < 0.001$) and non-hypertensive groups ($Z = -6.274, p <$

0.001), all these demonstrated significant changes. The alcoholics experienced a median loss of 16.0 ($Z = -2.665, p = 0.003$) and the non-alcoholics experienced a median loss of 15.0 ($Z = -8.507, p < 0.001$). Family history of smoking ($Z = -5.322, p < 0.001$) and non-smoking ($Z = -7.012, p < 0.001$) participants also exhibited statistically significant losses. Lifestyle stratification revealed the decrease in active ($Z = -5.442, p < 0.001$) and sedentary participants ($Z = -7.062, p < 0.001$). Dependent scores of rural participants ($Z = -7.167, p < 0.001$) and urban participants ($Z = -5.302, p < 0.001$) both revealed significant decrease with comparable median decreases. Altogether, stratified analysis reaffirmed that the intervention was significant for all demographic and clinical subgroups (Table-4).

DISCUSSION

In the present study, smoking cessation counseling in CAD patients was observed to have substantial and clinically significant reduction in smoking dependence. The Wilcoxon signed-rank test identified median reduction in smoking dependence scores from 29.0 pre-session to 14.0 at one-month follow-up ($Z = -8.928, p < 0.001$), which was robust statistical evidence of reduction in tobacco after counseling.

The Wilcoxon signed-rank test is particularly appropriate to assess paired non-normally distributed or ordinal data, as would be experienced in scales of smoking dependence. The extremely large negative Z-score indicates

Table-3: Wilcoxon signed-rank test assessing changes in smoking dependence scale scores between the pre-session and one-month follow-up.

Variable	N	Pre-session score (Median)	After 1 month score (Median)	Median change	Z-Score	P-Value
Smoking dependence score	105	29.0	14.0	15.0	-8.928	<0.001

Table-4: Stratified analysis of various variables with respect to changes in smoking dependence scale scores, using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test

Variables	N	Pre-session score (Median)	After 1 month score (Median)	Median Change	Z-Score	P-Value
Age (Year)						
≤ 40	52	29.0	14.0	15.0	-6.274	<0.001
≥ 41	53	29.0	14.0	15.0	-6.334	<0.001
CATEGORICAL VARIABLES						
Gender						
Male	95	29.0	14.0	15.0	-8.463	<0.001
Female	10	29.0	14.0	15.0	-2.803	<0.001
Type of CAD						
Single vessel	29	29.0	14.0	15.0	-4.703	<0.001
Double vessel	44	29.0	14.0	15.0	-5.776	<0.001
Triple vessel	32	29.0	14.0	15.0	-4.936	
Diabetes						
Yes	32	29.0	14.0	15.0	-4.936	<0.001
No	73	29.0	14.0	15.0	-7.424	<0.001
Hypertension						
Yes	53	29.0	14.0	15.0	-6.334	<0.001
No	52	29.0	14.0	15.0	-6.274	<0.001
Alcoholism						
Yes	9	30.0	14.0	16.0	-2.665	0.003
No	96	29.0	14.0	15.0	-8.507	<0.001
Family history of smoking						
Yes	41	29.0	14.0	15.0	-5.322	<0.001
No	64	29.0	14.0	15.0	-7.012	<0.001
Life style						
Active	39	29.0	14.0	15.0	-5.442	<0.001
Sedentary	66	29.0	14.0	15.0	-7.062	<0.001
Residence						
Urban	37	29.0	15.0	14.0	-5.302	<0.001
Rural	68	29.0	14.0	15.0	-7.167	<0.001

uniform direction of change in most patients. The median fall of 15 points-more than 50% reduction-is of direct clinical importance, indicating significant falls in levels of nicotine dependence within short-term boundaries. The significant finding, recorded despite the fact that data were not normally distributed, confirms that the intervention was indeed having a genuine, positive effect on the study participants.

This result supports prior work that set the fact that behavior intervention increases quit rates and lowers dependence scores significantly. Stead

et al., for instance, obtained a higher cessation success rate of 40–60% with formal counseling as compared to low advice.¹² Rigotti et al. also demonstrated hospital-based counseling among cardiovascular patients to lower levels of smoking and have a positive impact on long-term abstinence.¹³

Our findings also concur with a study by Cahill et al., which proved that the pairing of follow-up and behavioral support contributed immensely towards improved cessation.¹⁴ Kotz et al.¹⁵ further recorded a trial that indicated that intensive

interventions in heavy smokers, like CAD patients, had better quit rates compared to interventions in the general population.¹⁵ These findings cumulatively prove that counseling not only attenuates dependence but is also clinically significant towards CAD treatment.

Other than statistical significance, the 15-point reduction on the dependence scale by itself is a clinically important result. Research shows that even reduction in dependence is associated with reduced risk of cardiovascular events and improved treatment compliance.¹⁶ Our results also agree with research indicating that smoking cessation can have profound effect on prognosis and health-related quality of life even in patients with fixed coronary artery disease.¹⁷

In our present study, stratified analysis revealed uniform reductions in smoking dependence scores across groups, with all comparisons significant at $p < 0.05$. Men and women, and comorbidity and age groups all had a common median 15-point reduction, establishing generalizability of the intervention.

The high rates of comorbidities like diabetes (30.5%) and hypertension (50.5%) also strongly reflect the clinical significance of smoking abstinence, especially in light of the proven association between tobacco consumption and cardiovascular morbidity.¹⁸ Note that substantial benefits were noted regardless of gender, age, or CAD category, in keeping with evidence that smoking cessation therapies are effective across populations.¹⁴

Limitations of the study

The main limitation of this research is the extreme demographic imbalance in the gender split. 90.5% was male and a mere 9.5% was female. It becomes challenging to make generalizable conclusions regarding the effectiveness of the intervention in the female population. While the female subgroup did register a statistically significant decrease in scores, the limited sample size prohibits any conclusive statements regarding the overall impact in this population.

CONCLUSION

This study showed that the intervention to stop smoking worked very strongly to decrease participants' scores for smoking dependence. The statistically significant decrease across the whole sample and in all but one subgroup confirms the strong effectiveness of the positive influence of the intervention. Although results are generally applicable, statistical analysis indicates the effect magnitude could be influenced by some demographic and clinical variables.

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